

Suicide: Overview on The Preventive Legal Mechanisms in Bangladesh

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Dissecting Concepts

Introduction

Suicide is a topic sensitive enough to create confusion on whether to write on or not. It is a taboo in Bangladesh.¹ In this paper, there was an attempt to canvass the dilemma regarding openly discussing suicide. However, later on considering the Covid-19 pandemic and related mental health issues, learning about many alarming articles like *Is the Pandemic Sparking Suicide?* and *Suicide Rates Increasing in Several Demographics* – he decided to speak up.

Suicide is a topic with which various disciplines are related and it is difficult, to sum up, all the aspects in a small space. Therefore, he would like to focus mostly on the situation of the Bangladeshi legal system. But he will also provide some interdisciplinary and personal observations which might suggest the steps to be taken regarding the legal and the institutional arrangements to enable us to fight this problem efficiently.

Suicide Defined

The term suicide came from Latin *suī* (“one’s own”) and *cīda* (“one who kills”). According to *Issues in Law and Medicine (volume 3)*, Suicide is “the act of taking one’s own life”. In Bangladeshi laws, there is no clear legal definition of the term suicide. In absence of a clear definition legal practitioners and judges are bound to rely upon the general definitions of suicide, which indicates the need for a special law backed by strong legal, psychological, and social doctrines. Therefore, to analyse the legal aspects of suicide, first, we must try to find out the

underlying psychological, social, economic and other related factors.

Factors Behind Suicide

When a person finds that it is easier for them to kill themselves rather than living a life full of unbearable pain, trauma, and hopelessness then they commit suicide. Major causes of suicide include frustration regarding career or life, domestic violence, physical or sexual assault, demands for dowry, etc. British Journal of Psychiatry indicates that mental disorders, such as depression, alcoholism, drug addiction, and schizophrenia may also result in suicide. For example, in the suicide case of Comedian Robin Williams. It was reported that he became addicted to cocaine during the late 1970s and early 1980s. He quit cocaine after a friend’s demise. However, this event led Robin Williams to major depression, which is thought to be a leading cause of his death.²

Moreover, the lack of awareness regarding suicide is also a major reason especially in societies like Bangladesh where suicide is still a taboo topic. In most cases, suicidal people cannot find necessary mental health support and they feel that they are suffering alone. This

hopelessness is one major factor behind the high rate of suicide in Bangladesh.

Now let's look into the statistics regarding suicide and analyse how serious this issue is.

Statistical Analysis

A 2010 report by Shaheed Suhrawardy Medical College Hospital, Dhaka, suggests around 65,00,000 people of Bangladesh are prone to suicide. The rate is 128.08 people per 100,000 commit suicide every year and 89% of whom were women.³ Police records are the only institutional data available regarding suicide cases and the records show that the numbers of suicide have increased over the years. Around 6,753 people have committed suicide from January to July in 2019. This means, every day some 32 people committed suicide. Yet, experts believe the numbers are only a fraction of the reality. The concern is, without proper data, it is hard to understand the mental state in our country, where to prioritize, and how to formulate policies.⁴

Now, let's have a look at how the legal system is acting based on this decayed institutional arrangement.

The situation of Bangladeshi Legal System

The legal systems around the world are divided into two camps: in one camp there are European countries like Belgium, Luxemburg, the Netherlands, and Switzerland, etc. where the process of voluntary suicide is legal. In other countries like Bangladesh, China, Pakistan and, Saudi Arabia, etc. where suicide is a crime, and a

person who fails to commit suicide faces criminal charges.

In Bangladesh, the parent act dealing with suicide is the Penal Code 1860, wherein section 305, 306, and 309: Abetment of suicide of child or insane person, Abetment of suicide and Attempt to suicide has been criminalized. One assisting others to commit suicide may even face a death sentence. Moreover, a person who prepares to suicide or fails to commit suicide may also face imprisonment.

But whether in practice the existing laws are enough for the situation or they are archaic and lack scientific expertise? Let's try to find out.

Analysis and Recommended Reforms

The provisions in the Penal Code, 1860 seem insufficient to deal with all the aspects of suicide. Especially section 309, which incriminates a suicidal person is a barbaric and archaic provision. Under article 32 of the constitution one's protection of the right to life and personal liberty is a Fundamental Right and also part II of the Constitution depicts the Fundamental Principles of State Policies, encouraging the state to work for the socio-economic betterment of the people. So, in the spirit of the constitution, the state must show responsibility to arrange institutional and legal mechanisms to support the suicidal people. Therefore, it is highly recommended to create a special law like The Suicide Act, 1961 of England and Wales. Until then the judiciary of Bangladesh can play a progressive role following the path of the Indian judiciary through the famous case *State of Maharashtra v Maruti Shripati Dubal* to exempt patients of suicide-prone diseases (schizophrenia, giddiness, fright, reduced sleep etc.) from being convicted for attempted suicide.

Moreover, Prime Minister Sheikh Hasina's already instructed to set up an institute dedicated to studying suicides, but very little has been done in this regard. It should be done fast especially considering the Covid-19 connected mental health issues. Also, the decriminalization of suicide and the social acceptability of those who have attempted suicide must be ensured. Even legal provisions can be introduced penalizing any

discrimination toward those who have attempted suicide and thus a social reform through law may be possible to ensure the safety of the most vulnerable.

Conclusion

People are losing their loved ones, families are losing their only earning members, the country and its institutions are losing brilliant brains in suicide incidents. As the COVID-19 pandemic is hitting the country hard, there is a high risk of increasing suicide among the people for economic depression, physical and mental health problems.⁵ But we are still using the age-old laws and institutions and these are seemingly working as tools to punish the act of suicide rather than to prevent it. The presented statistics prove that such legal and institutional mechanisms have already failed to encounter the problem and if they do not evolve according to this current crisis, the risk is high that there will be more and more suicide attempts and suicide cases burdening the legal system and the society. So, special laws must be introduced which accommodate psychological, social, and economic understandings to evaluate and encounter the causes of suicide, especially in the current context. Trained and specialized institutions must be made to provide mental health support to suicidal people. And because of the Covid-19

pandemic and the associated mental health issues, this the high time to bring the aforesaid legal and institutional reforms or otherwise in near future the nation might find itself suffering from a higher rate of suicide.

¹ WHO, 'Suicide Prevention Day' (10 September 2017) World Health Organization
<<https://www.who.int/bangladesh/news/detail/10-09-2017-suicide-prevention-day>> accessed 10 July 2020?

² Tohid Hassaan, 'Robin Williams' suicide: a case study' (September 2016) SCIELO
<https://www.scielo.br/scielo.php?script=sci_arttext&pid=S2237-60892016000300178#B16> accessed 25 July 2020.

³ BBN, 'Survey says Bangladesh's 65 million people of suicide-prone' (11 December 2010) Bangladesh Business News
<<https://businessnews-bd.net/survey-says-bangladeshs-65-million-people-of-suicide-prone/>> accessed 10 July 2020.

⁴ Kamrul Hasan, 'World Suicide Prevention Day: What is Bangladesh doing to reduce the risk of suicide?' (10 September 2019) Dhaka Tribune
<<https://www.dhakatribune.com/bangladesh/2019/09/10/world-suicide-prevention-day-what-is-bangladesh-doing-to-reduce-the-risk-of-suicide>> accessed 10 July 2020

⁵ Mohammed Mamun and Mark Griffith, 'First COVID-19 suicide case in Bangladesh due to fear of COVID-19 and xenophobia: Possible suicide prevention strategies' (Apr 7 2020) PMC
<<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC7139250/>> accessed 10 July 2020.

Euthanasia

The practice of intentionally ending a life to relieve pain and suffering is known as Euthanasia. Different countries have different euthanasia laws. The British House of Lords select committee on medical ethics defines euthanasia as “a deliberate intervention undertaken with the express intention of ending a life, to relieve intractable suffering.” In the Netherlands and Belgium, euthanasia is understood as “termination of life by a doctor at the request of a patient”. The Dutch law, however, does not use the term 'euthanasia' but includes the concept under the broader definition of “assisted suicide and termination of life on request”. In Bangladesh, however, there is no legal basis to support an act of euthanasia.